

Full Length Article

Thermodynamic data for CO₂ absorption in aqueous 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ) solutions: CO₂ solubility, N₂O solubility, heat of absorption of CO₂, pH and liquid speciation

Diego Morlando, Ardi Hartono, Hanna K. Knuutila*

Department of Chemical Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, N-7491 Trondheim, Norway

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ABSTRACT

New thermodynamic data for CO₂ absorption in aqueous blends of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ) are measured in this work. The CO₂ solubility in aqueous AMP/PZ solutions, including the CESAR1 blend, was measured at temperatures from 40 to 150 °C, extending the range of CO₂ loading and temperature previously investigated.

The heat of absorption of CO₂ of aqueous AMP and AMP/PZ solutions was measured from 40 to 80 °C. The results indicate that the heat of absorption is constant with the temperature but it is affected by the AMP/PZ concentration ratio.

The N₂O solubility in the CESAR1 solvent was measured from 25 to 80 °C and up to CO₂ loading of 0.52 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine}. The N₂O solubility decreases as a function of temperature and CO₂ loading as a result of the salting-out effect.

The effect of CO₂, AMP and PZ concentration on the pH was experimentally determined. Liquid speciation for the CESAR1 blend and an aqueous solution of 1.5 M AMP + 0.75 M PZ was measured at CO₂ loading from 0 to 0.80 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine}. The results indicate that the CO₂ dissolved exists mainly as PZ-carbamate at relatively low CO₂ loading up to 0.40 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine}, while at higher CO₂ loading, the bicarbonate/carbonate and PZ-dicarbamate are the major products. The AMP carbamate is not a major product across the whole range of CO₂ concentration investigated.

The experimental data broaden the existing dataset and can support the development of rigorous thermodynamic models essential for evaluating energy requirements and environmental impacts of CO₂ capture using CESAR1 technology.

Introduction

Carbon capture is essential to minimize anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. Chemical absorption using amine aqueous solutions is one of the most suitable technology to decarbonize industries with high CO₂ emissions. A promising solvent technology is a blend of 3 M 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and 1.5 M piperazine (PZ), also known as CESAR1. Feron et al. (2020) first proposed this technology as new benchmark solvent for amine-based CO₂ capture. Morlando et al. (2024a) reviewed the current available knowledge for the CESAR1 solvent and outlined the existing experimental gaps. In their work, gaps in experimental data on thermodynamic properties are detected. Thermodynamic properties are crucial to develop models for the design of CO₂ capture plants.

The key thermodynamic experimental gaps highlighted in Morlando et al. (2024a) are shortly summarized in this section along with the significance of obtaining these data.

The CESAR1 is a blend of two amines. Hence, the vapour liquid equilibrium (VLE) properties for the single subsystems, AMP/H₂O/CO₂ and PZ/H₂O/CO₂, must be correctly characterized when a rigorous thermodynamic framework is developed (Hartono et al., 2021a). Hartono et al. (2021a) and Kim (2009) measured the differential heat of absorption of CO₂ in 26.8 mass % and 25.0 mass % aqueous AMP solutions, respectively. The data are not in agreement with each other and deviations between the measurements are higher than 40 %. Arcis et al. (2007) measured integral heat of absorption data in 15 and 30 mass % aqueous AMP solutions, the data shows a weak de-

* Corresponding author at: Department of Chemical Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
E-mail address: hanna.knuutila@ntnu.no (H.K. Knuutila).

Property	AMP/H ₂ O	PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂
Density	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Viscosity	Green	Green	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow
Diffusivity	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Red	Red
Kinetics	Green	Green	Yellow	Red	Green	Red
VLE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow
CO ₂ Henry's constant	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Red
Speciation	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Degradation	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
ΔH _{abs}	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green

Property	AMP/H ₂ O	PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂
Density	Green	Green	Morlando et al. (2024)	Green	Green	Morlando et al. (2024)
Viscosity	Green	Green	Morlando et al. (2024)	Red	Green	Morlando et al. (2024)
Diffusivity	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Red	Red
Kinetics	Green	Green	Yellow	Red	Green	Red
VLE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	This work
CO ₂ Henry's constant	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	This Work
Speciation	Green	Green	This Work	Green	Green	This Work
Degradation	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
ΔH _{abs}	Green	Green	Green	This Work	Green	This Work

Fig. 1. Qualitative maps of the experimental gaps in the literature concerning the CESAR1 solvent. Left (Before this work and Morlando et al. (2024b)) available in Morlando et al. (2024a), Right (After this work and Morlando et al. (2024b)). Data unavailable (red), gaps identified (yellow), and data available (green).

pendency on the CO₂ loading compared to Hartono et al. (2021a) and Kim (2009). Given the blended nature of the CESAR1 solvent, accurate characterization of the thermodynamics of the AMP/H₂O/CO₂ is needed to model the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system. CO₂ solubility data and heat of absorption of CO₂ data are measured for an aqueous solution of 3 M (26.8 mass %) AMP in a temperature range from 40 to 80 °C since CO₂ solubility data for aqueous AMP solutions at relevant concentrations of the CESAR1 blend are scattered at lower temperatures.

CO₂ solubility data for the CESAR1 solvent are limited to 120 °C, (Brüder et al. (2011); Hartono et al. (2021a)). The pressure in the desorber section is usually limited to 2 bar, i.e. temperature generally lower than 120–125 °C, to limit thermal degradation. Long-term pilot plant testing has shown that the CESAR1 solvent is more stable than aqueous 30 mass % ethanolamine (MEA) (Mosser et al., 2023). High-pressure stripping could potentially reduce the energy requirement for the stripper, (Rochelle, 2012), reducing also the capital and operative costs for the CO₂ compression stage. In this work, we have broadened the CO₂ solubility dataset for the CESAR1 blend to temperatures up to 150 °C. These experimental data are essential to quantitatively and accurately investigate the benefits of high-pressure stripping for the CESAR1 solvent. Furthermore, we investigated the CO₂ solubility and the heat of absorption of CO₂ trend as a function of AMP/PZ concentration at different temperatures. Data at different AMP/PZ concentrations were collected to understand the individual contribution of the amine to the measured equilibrium properties. These data can be used for the development of thermodynamic frameworks that are flexible to the amine concentration change and provide an understanding of the impact of the individual amine on the thermodynamics properties investigated.

Morlando et al. (2024a) also noted the absence of N₂O solubility data for CESAR1. N₂O solubility data have been widely used in thermodynamics and kinetics modelling (Frailie et al., 2011; Hartono et al., 2020; Hartono et al., 2021b). These data are used to estimate the CO₂ Henry's constant via the N₂O analogy (Monteiro et al., 2015). The CO₂ Henry's constant is a crucial part of the thermodynamic framework since it defines the concentration of the free CO₂ in the mixed solvent. It also largely affects the calculation of the experimental kinetics constants (Monteiro et al., 2015). In this work, we measured the N₂O solubility, expressed as N₂O Henry's constant, for the CESAR1 blend as a function of temperature and CO₂ concentration.

Lastly, speciation data, describing the distribution of molecular and ionic species as function of CO₂ loading, are unavailable for CESAR1. They constitute an important part of the thermodynamic framework used in modelling and they impact the modelling of kinetics. To address this knowledge gap, this study provides new experimental data for the liquid speciation of the CESAR1 blend by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). Additionally, the solvent basicity pH was also experimentally investigated as a function of the amine and CO₂ concentrations.

Thus, to summarize, new experimental CO₂ solubility, heat of absorption of CO₂ data for the AMP/H₂O/CO₂ system and CO₂ solubility, heat of absorption of CO₂, N₂O solubility, pH and liquid speciation data for the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system are obtained in this work. The measurements in this work fill many of the experimental gaps on the thermodynamic properties for the CESAR1 blend highlighted by Morlando et al. (2024a). Fig. 1 shows an overview of the main experimental gaps for the CESAR1 solvent as presented by Morlando et al. (2024a) and after the experimental results obtained in this work and Morlando et al. (2024b). This work provides experimental data on the thermodynamic properties of CO₂ absorption in the CESAR1 solvent. Moreover, the new data offer valuable insights into the primary reaction mechanisms involved in CO₂ absorption by CESAR1. These data are essential for developing a reliable thermodynamic model that can serve as the basis for designing the process unit in a CO₂ capture plant.

Materials and experimental setup

The chemicals used in this work, the providers and their purity are reported in Table 1 and they were used without further purification.

Aqueous AMP and AMP/PZ solutions have been prepared gravimetrically and volumetrically in a 1 dm³ flask using a Mettler Toledo MS6002S with an accuracy of 10⁻⁵ kg. The prepared solutions were stirred overnight and then used for the experiments. CO₂ loaded solutions were prepared gravimetrically by bubbling CO₂ through a sparger and recording the change in mass using the same scale reported above. The amine concentration was measured by acid-base titration while the CO₂ content by inorganic carbon analysis (IC). The reported CO₂ contents are based on the analyzed values except for the CO₂ solubility and heat of absorption of CO₂ experiments, where the CO₂ content is calculated by mass balance. More information on the CO₂ loading analysis and amine titration and their uncertainty can be found in our previous work (Morlando et al., 2024b).

Experimental setups

The experimental setups and the methodology used in this work are described below.

Calorimeter. A reaction calorimeter, CPA 202 provided by ChemiSens AB was used to measure the CO₂ solubility, as total pressure measurements, and the heat of absorption of CO₂. The calorimeter consists of a glass reactor ($V_r = 270 \text{ cm}^3$) with a mechanical stirrer, one pressure transducer (0 – 1000 kPa) ($u(P_r) = 0.2 \text{ kPa}$), and a Pt-100 temperature sensor ($u(T_r) = 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Around 125 g of the prepared unloaded solution is filled into the reactor which is then submerged in a bath of diethylene glycol. The reactor is evacuated at ambient pressure to around 4 kPa, and the temperature is set to the desired value. The CO₂ is stored in a stainless-steel vessel ($V_r = 2300 \text{ cm}^3$), and its temperature and pressure are recorded with a temperature and pressure transducer

Table 1
Chemicals used in this work.

Component	Abbreviation	CAS No.	Structure	Purity	Source
2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol	AMP	124-68-5		>99.0 % (Titration with HClO ₄)	Thermo-Fischer
Piperazine	PZ	110-85-0		>99.0 % (GC)	Thermo-Fischer
Ethanolamine	MEA	141-43-5		>99.0 % (GC)	Sigma-Aldrich
Carbon dioxide	CO ₂	124-38-9		>99.999 %	Yara-Praxair
1,4-Dioxane	-	123-01-1		>99 %	Thermo-Fischer
Deuterium oxide	D ₂ O	7789-20-0		99.9 %	Sigma-Aldrich

The purity has been obtained by the COA (Certificate of Analysis).

with the same specifications. The CO₂ is injected at the bottom of the reactor and the amount of CO₂ injected is calculated by mass balance using the recorded pressure and temperature change in the vessel. The Peng-Robinson equation of state is used to perform this calculation. The equilibrium is considered to be reached when the temperature, the pressure and the total power are constant for 10 min, as also was done in Hartono et al. (2021a). The amount of heat removed to keep the solution to the constant set temperature is calculated by integration of the recorded power as a function of time and it is assumed to be equal to the heat of absorption of CO₂. Further details on the calculation of the heat of absorption and the integration of the recorded power are available in the supplementary material, Figure S1. A schematic of the calorimeter is available in Fig. 2.

The total pressure measurements and the experimental methodology have been validated by measuring the CO₂ solubility for aqueous 30 mass % MEA at 40 °C and 120 °C. The experimental data collected in this work are available in Table S1 and agrees very well with the data collected by Wanderley et al. (2020) and Aronu et al. (2011), Figure S2. The heat of absorption of CO₂ has been measured for 30 mass % MEA at 40 °C and the data are available in Table S1. The measured differential heat of absorption agrees well with the data collected by Wanderley et al. (2020), Figure S2. To further improve the validity of our experimental methodology, the last sample of selected experiments was collected, and the CO₂ content and amine concentration were measured to verify the accuracy of the mass balance. The CO₂ loadings calculated from the mass balance agree with the analytically determined values within 2.5 % absolute average relative deviation (AARD). For some experiments, the end sample could not be analyzed because it precipitated at room temperature and ambient pressure. Further information on this can be found in the supplementary material, Table S2.

Fig. 2. Schematics of the CPA202 reaction calorimeter. Figure taken from Hartono et al., 2017.

The uncertainty for the equilibrium total pressure and CO₂ loading was calculated using the approach developed by Wanderley et al. (2020) but the heat of absorption uncertainty was estimated differently. The apparatus is equipped with a validation electric heater which was set to provide 3600 J to the system before the experiment started and the energy is calculated by integration of the power profile. The deviation of the measured energy from the one provided by the heater is used as the uncertainty of the power measurement. The uncertainties on the measured power and the calculated amount of CO₂ injected are considered to be the main contributors to the uncertainty of the heat of absorption.

In this work, the CO₂ solubility measurements are reported as total solvent pressure and CO₂ partial pressure. The partial pressure of CO₂ has been calculated by subtracting the recorded total pressure at a specific loading, α , with the solvent partial pressure without CO₂. The uncertainty of the CO₂ partial pressure increases at low CO₂ concentrations due to the accuracy of the pressure transducer. Therefore, only results with CO₂ partial pressure higher than 1 kPa are reported.

For the AMP/H₂O/CO₂ system, the CO₂ solubility and the CO₂ heat of absorption of aqueous 3 M AMP are measured at 40, 60 and 80 °C. The CO₂ solubility for the CESAR1 solvent is measured from 40 to 150 °C. The heat of absorption for the CESAR1 solvent is measured at 40 °C and 80 °C. Morlando et al. (2024a) reported that the PZ concentrations in pilot campaigns span from 5.0 to 17.0 mass %. Thus, two more AMP/PZ ratios were studied, while keeping overall amine concentration fixed at 40 mass %. The AMP/PZ molar ratios of 1.5 and 6.8 (correspond-

Fig. 3. Schematics of the N₂O solubility apparatus. Figure taken from Aronu et al., 2012.

Table 2CO₂ solubility and heat of absorption data for an aqueous solution of 3.0 M (26.8 mass %) AMP.

313.15 K					333.15 K					353.15 K				
α	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot}	P_{CO_2}	$-\Delta H_{abs}$	α	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot}	P_{CO_2}	$-\Delta H_{abs}$	α	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot}	P_{CO_2}	$-\Delta H_{abs}$
[-]		[kPa]	[kPa]	[$\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}}$]	[-]		[kPa]	[kPa]	[$\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}}$]	[-]		[kPa]	[kPa]	[$\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}}$]
0	0	8.0	-	-	0	0	21.0	-	-	0	0	50.8	-	-
0.06	0.01	8.3	*	87.0	0.06	0.01	21.2	*	86.9	0.06	0.01	52.7	1.9	91.3
0.13	0.01	8.5	*	89.5	0.12	0.01	21.6	*	88.8	0.13	0.01	55.5	4.7	88.1
0.19	0.01	8.6	*	89.3	0.19	0.01	22.3	1.3	85.8	0.19	0.01	59.2	8.4	87.3
0.25	0.01	8.8	*	85.2	0.25	0.01	23.3	2.3	82.1	0.25	0.01	64.3	13.5	84.7
0.31	0.01	9.1	1.0	84.4	0.31	0.01	24.6	3.6	79.5	0.31	0.01	70.9	20.1	83.3
0.37	0.01	9.5	1.4	81.7	0.37	0.01	26.4	5.3	75.8	0.37	0.01	79.6	28.8	82.1
0.44	0.01	10.1	2.0	78.4	0.43	0.01	28.9	7.8	73.8	0.43	0.02	90.7	39.9	80.1
0.50	0.02	11.0	3.0	73.5	0.49	0.02	32.5	11.4	68.4	0.49	0.02	105.9	55.1	78.2
0.56	0.02	12.4	4.4	69.3	0.55	0.02	37.5	16.5	65.5	0.55	0.02	126.1	75.3	76.6
0.62	0.02	14.7	6.7	65.1	0.61	0.02	45.1	24.0	64.5	0.61	0.02	154.5	103.7	74.1
0.69	0.02	18.4	10.4	61.0	0.67	0.02	56.1	35.1	69.1	0.67	0.02	194.3	143.5	71.6
0.75	0.02	24.9	16.9	58.0	0.73	0.02	73.3	52.3	65.0	0.73	0.02	249.6	198.8	70.1
0.81	0.02	36.5	28.4	53.5	0.79	0.02	101.4	80.4	62.3	0.78	0.02	327.2	276.4	66.8
0.87	0.02	59.8	51.8	50.8	0.84	0.02	148.0	126.9	58.0	0.83	0.02	434.6	383.8	52.6
0.92	0.02	112.4	104.4	46.2	0.90	0.02	230.2	209.1	55.5	0.87	0.02	575.6	524.8	41.1
0.97	0.02	233.4	225.4	41.8	0.94	0.02	369.2	348.1	52.8	-	-	-	-	-
1.00	0.02	453.8	445.7	38.7	0.97	0.02	569.2	548.2	48.2	-	-	-	-	-
1.01	0.02	659.8	651.8	38.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

a) $\alpha = \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}}$

b) $u(T) = 0.1 K$

c) $u(P_{tot}) = 0.2 kPa$

d) P_{CO_2} was estimated according to: $P_{CO_2} = P_{tot,\alpha} - P_{tot,\alpha=0} \cdot P_{CO_2}$ was not estimated due to high uncertainty.

ing to PZ concentration of 15.7 mass % and 5.0 mass %) were also measured.

The N₂O solubility apparatus. The N₂O solubility apparatus consists of a glass reactor ($V_r = 1033.25 cm^3$), a mechanical stirrer, two pressure transducers of different scales (0 – 600 kPa) and (0 – 200 kPa), and two Pt-100 temperature sensors located for the liquid and gas phases $u(T_r) = 0.1 ^\circ C$. The reactor is evacuated and filled with a measured amount of solvent of around 400 g. The reactor is then evacuated again to remove any dissolved gas. A condenser, set at 4 °C, is used to minimize the solvent loss during the second evacuation. The N₂O is stored in a stainless still vessel whose pressure and temperature are recorded by a PTX 610 pressure transducer (0 – 600 kPa) and a Pt-100 temperature sensor $u(T_r) = 0.1 ^\circ C$. The equilibrium solvent pressure, i.e. without any addition of N₂O, is recorded at different temperatures. The N₂O is injected at the highest temperature and after equilibrium is attained, the temperature is then reduced to measure a new equilibrium point. The

equilibrium is assumed reached when the pressure variance is lower than 0.5 kPa and the difference between the temperature in the gas and the liquid phase lower than 0.1 °C for at least ten minutes. The amount of N₂O injected is calculated by mass balance using the Peng-Robinson equation of state and recorded pressure and temperature change in the vessel. The equilibrium amount of N₂O in the gas phase at each temperature is calculated by the difference between the equilibrium pressure after the N₂O injection and the equilibrium solvent pressure. The amount of N₂O in the liquid phase, i.e. the N₂O solubility, is calculated by mass balance. A schematic of the N₂O solubility apparatus is available in Fig. 3.

The experimental methodology has been validated by measuring the N₂O solubility in water, as shown in Table S3. The experimental results expressed as N₂O Henry's constants, agree well with the data collected by Jou et al. (1992) and Li et al. (1995), with an AARD of respectively 1.3 % and 3.9 %, as shown in Figure S4.

Fig. 4. CO₂ solubility data for 3 M AMP aqueous solution, (a) total pressure (b) CO₂ partial pressure. (● This work, □ Hartono et al. (2020) for CO₂ partial pressure and Hartono et al. (2021a) for total pressure, Δ Tontiwachwuthikul et al. (1991), + Yang et al. (2010), ◇ Roberts et al. (1988)). (Black 40 °C, Blue 60 °C, Red 80 °C).

Table 3
CO₂ solubility and heat of absorption data for aqueous the AMP /PZ solutions investigated in this work.

24.4 mass % AMP + 15.7 mass % PZ																	
313.15 K					333.15 K					353.15 K							
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$
0	0	6.0	-	-	-	0	0	17.9	-	-	-	0	0	42.7	-	-	-
0.04	0.00	6.2	*	91.8	6	0.04	0.00	17.9	*	99.0	7	0.04	0.00	42.8	*	100.7	6
0.08	0.01	6.3	*	90.5	5	0.08	0.01	17.9	*	93.4	6	0.09	0.01	42.9	*	97.5	6
0.12	0.01	6.5	*	91.6	5	0.13	0.01	18.0	*	91.0	6	0.13	0.01	43.1	*	92.5	6
0.16	0.01	6.6	*	91.2	5	0.17	0.01	18.1	*	96.5	6	0.17	0.01	43.5	*	90.2	5
0.21	0.01	6.7	*	93.0	6	0.21	0.01	18.1	*	97.3	6	0.21	0.01	44.0	1.4	98.4	6
0.25	0.01	6.9	*	93.2	6	0.25	0.01	18.7	*	100.0	7	0.26	0.01	44.8	2.1	92.5	6
0.29	0.01	7.0	*	94.1	6	0.30	0.01	18.9	*	95.9	6	0.30	0.01	45.8	3.1	90.3	5
0.33	0.01	7.1	1.1	94.3	6	0.34	0.01	19.2	1.3	94.0	6	0.34	0.01	47.3	4.7	93.1	6
0.37	0.01	7.3	1.3	91.5	5	0.38	0.01	19.7	1.8	93.3	6	0.38	0.01	49.6	6.9	88.4	5
0.42	0.01	7.5	1.4	91.1	5	0.42	0.01	20.3	2.4	93.2	6	0.42	0.01	52.7	10.0	88.1	5
0.46	0.01	7.6	1.6	89.6	5	0.47	0.01	21.2	3.4	89.7	6	0.46	0.01	57.3	14.7	86.5	5
0.50	0.01	7.9	1.9	88.2	5	0.51	0.01	22.8	4.9	88.2	6	0.50	0.01	64.1	21.5	86.0	5
0.54	0.01	8.4	2.3	85.5	5	0.55	0.01	25.1	7.3	85.0	6	0.55	0.01	74.2	31.5	81.3	5
0.59	0.01	9.0	3.0	83.7	5	0.59	0.01	29.0	11.2	81.2	5	0.59	0.01	89.3	46.7	78.5	5
0.63	0.01	10.1	4.1	78.4	5	0.64	0.01	35.6	17.7	75.3	5	0.63	0.01	111.9	69.3	72.1	4
0.67	0.01	12.0	6.0	71.8	4	0.68	0.01	46.8	28.9	71.9	5	0.66	0.01	146.0	103.4	68.5	4
0.72	0.01	15.7	9.7	65.2	4	0.72	0.01	66.5	48.6	67.6	4	0.70	0.01	198.1	155.5	73.3	4
0.76	0.01	23.0	17.0	55.5	3	0.76	0.02	99.5	81.6	60.9	4	0.74	0.01	272.6	230.0	66.6	4
0.80	0.01	37.0	31.0	51.5	3	0.80	0.02	153.5	135.6	57.0	4	0.77	0.02	376.4	333.7	59.5	4
0.84	0.01	62.5	56.5	46.8	3	0.83	0.02	236.6	218.7	47.8	3	0.80	0.02	498.5	455.8	60.6	4
0.87	0.02	106.9	100.9	43.7	3	0.86	0.02	354.3	336.5	44.4	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.91	0.02	178.4	172.4	39.1	2	0.89	0.02	483.8	465.9	50.4	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.94	0.02	284.3	278.3	37.0	2	0.90	0.02	570.3	552.4	34.3	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
35.0 mass % AMP + 5.0 mass % PZ																	
313.15 K					333.15 K					353.15 K							
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$
0	0	7.3	-	-	-	0	0	20.1	-	-	-	0	0	48.5	-	-	-
0.08	0.00	7.3	*	104.6	7	0.06	0.00	20.1	*	97.3	5	0.06	0.00	50.8	2.3	97.4	4
0.16	0.01	7.3	*	102.2	7	0.13	0.01	20.3	*	95.6	5	0.12	0.01	53.1	4.7	93.6	4
0.24	0.01	7.4	*	100.4	7	0.19	0.01	20.7	*	93.4	5	0.18	0.01	56.3	7.9	91.6	4
0.32	0.01	7.8	*	94.0	7	0.25	0.01	21.4	1.3	91.8	5	0.24	0.01	60.6	12.2	88.9	4
0.40	0.01	8.4	1.1	87.7	6	0.31	0.01	22.7	2.6	88.7	5	0.30	0.01	66.6	18.1	87.0	4
0.48	0.01	9.6	2.3	84.1	6	0.38	0.01	24.7	4.6	87.2	4	0.36	0.01	75.2	26.8	83.2	4
0.56	0.01	12.0	4.7	76.5	5	0.44	0.01	27.9	7.8	83.7	4	0.42	0.01	88.6	40.2	81.3	4
0.64	0.01	17.2	9.9	68.9	5	0.50	0.01	32.8	12.7	80.7	4	0.48	0.01	107.9	59.4	78.8	4
0.72	0.01	29.1	21.9	62.1	4	0.56	0.01	40.9	20.7	76.1	4	0.54	0.01	136.5	88.0	76.0	3
0.79	0.01	58.4	51.1	55.0	4	0.63	0.01	54.0	33.9	71.5	4	0.60	0.01	179.3	130.8	72.7	3
0.86	0.01	118.2	111.0	49.0	3	0.69	0.01	76.6	56.5	67.2	3	0.65	0.01	244.2	195.7	70.7	3
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.75	0.01	116.2	96.1	64.3	3	0.70	0.01	340.1	291.6	65.9	3
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.80	0.01	185.9	165.8	58.4	3	0.74	0.01	432.9	384.4	63.6	3
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.76	0.01	509.5	461.0	57.6	3
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.77	0.01	564.9	516.4	52.5	3
26.6 mass % AMP + 12.8 mass % PZ																	
313.15 K					353.15 K												
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	$-\Delta H_{abs}$ $\left[\frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}} \right]$	$u(-\Delta H_{abs})$						
0	0	6.1	*	-	-	0	0	44.2	*	-	-						
0.08	0.00	6.1	*	92.7	7	0.06	0.00	44.6	*	95.7	5						
0.17	0.00	6.1	*	93.8	7	0.12	0.01	44.9	*	89.8	5						
0.25	0.01	6.2	*	96.3	7	0.18	0.01	45.5	1.4	87.5	5						
0.33	0.01	6.3	*	96.8	7	0.24	0.01	46.8	2.7	88.5	5						
0.42	0.01	6.5	*	95.5	7	0.31	0.01	49.0	4.9	91.7	5						
0.50	0.01	7.0	*	92.1	7	0.37	0.01	52.8	8.7	89.8	5						
0.56	0.01	8.0	1.9	84.7	6	0.43	0.01	59.1	14.9	87.4	5						
0.63	0.01	10.3	4.2	77.9	6	0.49	0.01	69.6	25.5	84.6	4						
0.69	0.01	15.9	9.8	67.6	5	0.55	0.01	87.7	43.6	79.1	4						
0.75	0.01	29.6	23.5	57.4	4	0.61	0.01	119.7	75.6	75.7	4						
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.67	0.01	176.6	132.4	73.1	4						
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.72	0.01	272.6	228.4	66.5	4						
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.76	0.01	385.8	341.6	62.2	3						

a) $\alpha = \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP} + mol_{PZ}}$

b) $u(T) = 0.1 K$

c) $u(P_{tot}) = 0.2 kPa$

d) P_{CO_2} was estimated according to: $P_{CO_2} = P_{tot,\alpha} - P_{tot,\alpha=0}$. * P_{CO_2} was not estimated due to high uncertainty.

The uncertainty for the CO₂ Henry's constant has been calculated for each point and the developed methodology is presented in the supplementary material.

The N₂O solubility for the CESAR1 blend is measured from 25 to 80 °C and for four different CO₂ loading: 0, 0.10, 0.30 and 0.50 $\frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{mol AMP} + \text{mol PZ}}$. For the experiments using CO₂-loaded CESAR1 solution, a sample was collected after the experiments and analyzed. The results showed that the CO₂ loading changed within a 5 % relative deviation which is considered satisfactory. Finally, a bench table calculation using the e-NRTL (electrolyte Non-Random Two-Liquid) model developed by Hartono et al. (2021a) has been carried out to check that at higher temperatures the stripping of CO₂ would not change significantly the CO₂ concentration in the liquid phase. The calculation shows that the loading should change by less than 1 %, which is lower than the relative uncertainty for the CO₂ loading measurement $u_r(\alpha) = 0.02$.

pH measurements. The basicity of the three solutions at different AMP/PZ molar ratios (2, 4 and 0.4) and total amine concentrations (40 % and 60 %) were measured at different CO₂ concentrations. Five vial samples were immersed in a Julabo-controlled water bath to maintain a constant temperature. A SevenEasy pH reading from a Mettler Toledo equipped with a robust LE 438 sensor was used and the pH sensor was calibrated at different pH levels (2, 4, 7, 9 and 12) at a constant temperature and at ambient pressure.

Liquid speciation measurements by NMR. A Bruker 600 MHz Avance III HD equipped with a 5-mm cryogenic CP-TCI z-gradient probe and SampleCase was used to measure the liquid speciation. Both 1D NMR (¹H/¹³C) and 2D NMR (¹H-¹H COSY, ¹H-¹³C HSQS and ¹H-¹³C HMBBC) were performed to elucidate all peaks present in the spectra (Ciftja et al., 2014). ¹³C was performed for the quantification of the species in the liquid mixture. The parameters for the quantification of the ¹³C are reported, together with the chemical shifts, in the supplementary information (see Table S5, Table S6 and Figure S6). The samples for the NMR analyses were filled into NMR tubes and the mass was recorded using a Mettler Toledo ME204, with a sensitivity of 0.0001 g. An internal reference standard was utilized to quantify the carbon present in the samples. A mixture of 50 mass % D₂O and 50 mass % 1,4-dioxane was prepared and filled into a 5 mm coaxial insert by Norell and it was used as a standard and lock solvent to provide a peak with a known chemical shift. The mass of the lock solvent was recorded using the Mettler Toledo ME204. Around 0.60 g of sample and 0.10 g of standard solution are needed for each analysis. The speciation of the CESAR1 blend has been measured in a loading range from 0 to 0.55 $\frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{mol AMP} + \text{mol PZ}}$. CESAR1 solution at loading higher than 0.60 $\frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{mol AMP} + \text{mol PZ}}$ could not be analyzed because of solid formation. Therefore, a solution of 20 mass % (AMP+PZ) with the same AMP/PZ molar ratio ($\frac{n_{\text{AMP}}}{n_{\text{PZ}}} = 2$) was also prepared and analyzed to be able to investigate the speciation up to CO₂ loading of 0.80 $\frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{mol AMP} + \text{mol PZ}}$.

The CO₂ loadings were calculated based on the quantitative results obtained using NMR and compared with the results obtained by the CO₂ and titration analyses. The results between the two analytical techniques, reported in Table S4 and Figure S5, show a relative deviation for the CO₂ loading of 1.9 % and 3.5 % for the CESAR1 and 20 mass % AMP + PZ solution respectively.

Results

CO₂ Solubility and heat of absorption of CO₂ for aqueous AMP solution. The experimental data for the CO₂ solubility of aqueous 3 M AMP solution are reported in Table 2. Fig. 4 shows the experimental total pressure and CO₂ partial pressure over an aqueous 3 M AMP solution. The equilibrium total pressures measured in this work agree well with the work by Hartono et al. (2021a) at 60 °C and 80 °C, however deviates with their data at 40 °C. The calculated CO₂ partial pressures have been compared with experimental literature data (Hartono et al.,

Fig. 5. Heat of absorption of CO₂ over an aqueous AMP solution. (● This work 3 M AMP, Δ Kim, (2009) 25.0 mass % AMP, □ Hartono et al. (2021a) 3 M AMP, ◇ Arcis et al., (2007) 30 mass % AMP. (Black 40 °C, Green 50 °C, Blue 60 °C, Red 80 °C).

2020; Roberts et al., 1988; Tontiwachwuthikul et al., 1991; Yang et al., 2010). The experimental results at 40, 60 and 80 °C agree very well with Hartono et al. (2020) in the CO₂ loading range investigated. The experimental CO₂ partial pressure data at 40 °C agree well with Roberts et al. (1988) and Yang et al. (2010) at CO₂ loading higher than 0.60 $\frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{mol AMP}}$, while they are slightly higher at lower CO₂ loading. The experimental data from Tontiwachwuthikul et al. (1991) are in worse agreement with the data collected in this work and the other literature sources at low CO₂ loading over the whole range of temperatures investigated.

The measured heat of absorption of CO₂ data for 3 M AMP are reported in Table 2. The experimental CO₂ heat of absorption data show a strongly decreasing functionality with the CO₂ loading. The AMP is a bicarbonate-forming solvent, Ciftja et al. (2014), and this strong decrease of the heat of absorption as a function of the CO₂ content is found also for tertiary amines solutions such as aqueous methyldiethanolamine MDEA solution (Kim et al., 2011). However, unlike tertiary amines such as MDEA, it has a relatively high heat of absorption at low CO₂ loading. The experimental heat of absorption of CO₂ seems to be constant with the temperature over the operative range investigated. The experimental heat of absorption data has been compared to literature data in Fig. 5. The results collected in this work are in great agreement with the ones collected by Kim (2009) at 40 °C and 80 °C. The data collected by Hartono et al. (2021a) are significantly lower than the one collected in this work and by Kim (2009). Kim (2009) used an apparatus that requires about 10 times more solvent than the apparatus used in this work and it has been discussed to have a better accuracy than the one used in this work (Wanderley et al., 2020). The experimental heat of absorption of CO₂ data by Arcis et al. (2007), integral in the CO₂ loading, are also slightly lower than the experimental data in this work. The difference is not explained by the reported uncertainty between the two sources.

CO₂ Solubility and heat of absorption of CO₂ for aqueous AMP/PZ solutions. The experimental data for the CO₂ solubility of aqueous CESAR1 solution are reported in Tables 3 and 4. Table 3 reported the experimental CO₂ solubility data for the CESAR1 solvent at lower temperature (40 and 80 °C). Table 4 reports the experimental CO₂ solubility data for the CESAR1 solvent at high temperature (110–150 °C). Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the VLE data for the CESAR1 blend collected in this work and literature data. The data from this work are in good agreement with the ones collected by Hartono et al. (2021a) and

Table 4High-pressure CO₂ solubility data for the CESAR1 Solvent, 26.6 mass % AMP and 12.8 mass % PZ [$\frac{mol_{AMP}}{mol_{PZ}} = 2$].

383.15 K				393.15 K				403.15 K				413.15 K				423.15 K			
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]
0	0	131.7	-	0	0	184.9	-	0	0	250.2	-	0	0	336.7	-	0	0	443.3	-
0.14	0.00	139.2	7.5	0.18	0.00	210.9	26.0	0.06	0.00	256.4	6.2	0.05	0.00	348.3	11.5	0.04	0.00	457.3	14.0
0.18	0.01	145.2	13.5	0.36	0.01	314.3	129.4	0.09	0.01	265.1	14.9	0.09	0.01	366.5	29.8	0.07	0.01	483.1	39.8
0.23	0.01	153.7	22.0	0.46	0.02	464.0	279.1	0.12	0.01	274.3	24.1	0.14	0.01	396.3	59.5	0.11	0.01	519.7	76.4
0.27	0.01	165.4	33.8	0.50	0.02	554.9	370.0	0.14	0.01	281.4	31.2	0.18	0.01	438.4	101.7	0.15	0.01	565.5	122.2
0.32	0.01	182.0	50.3	0.52	0.02	624.7	439.8	0.15	0.01	286.8	36.6	0.22	0.01	489.1	152.3	0.18	0.01	622.0	178.7
0.36	0.01	204.5	72.9	0.54	0.03	645.5	460.5	0.17	0.01	292.7	42.5	0.26	0.01	549.2	212.4	0.22	0.01	692.9	249.7
0.41	0.01	234.9	103.3	II Run				II Run				0.30	0.01	609.5	272.7	-	-	-	-
0.45	0.01	275.6	143.9	0	0	185.5	-	0	0	249.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.49	0.01	328.9	197.2	0.10	0.00	193.6	8.1	0.07	0.00	260.0	10.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.53	0.01	398.9	267.2	0.20	0.01	215.9	30.4	0.14	0.01	282.3	32.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	0.29	0.01	261.5	76.0	0.21	0.01	321.5	71.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	0.38	0.01	344.4	158.9	0.28	0.01	385.0	135.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	0.46	0.01	471.3	285.8	0.35	0.01	478.0	228.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	0.52	0.01	612.3	426.8	0.41	0.01	615.8	366.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

a) $\alpha = \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP} + mol_{PZ}}$

b) $u(T) = 0.1 K$

c) $u(P_{tot}) = 0.2 kPa$

d) P_{CO_2} was estimated according to: $P_{CO_2} = P_{tot,\alpha} - P_{tot,\alpha=0}$. * P_{CO_2} was not estimated due to high uncertainty.

Fig. 6. CO₂ solubility data for the CESAR1 blend (a) total pressure (b) CO₂ partial pressure. (● This work, □ Hartono et al. (2021a), Δ Brüder et al. (2011)). (Black 40 °C, Red 80 °C, Orange 110 °C, Purple 120 °C, Green 130 °C, Blue 140 °C, Cyan 150 °C).

Fig. 7. Comparison of the CO₂ solubility (a) and the heat of absorption of CO₂ (b) for the three concentrations studied in this work (● 26.6 mass % AMP 12.8 mass % PZ CESAR1, ■ 24.4 mass % AMP 15.7 mass % PZ, ▲ 35.0 mass % AMP 5.0 mass % PZ), (Black 40 °C, Red 80 °C, Purple 120 °C).

Brüder et al. (2011), indicating good reliability of the data collected at higher temperatures. The CO₂ solubility data for the two other AMP/PZ ($\frac{n_{AMP}}{n_{PZ}} = 1.5$ and $\frac{n_{AMP}}{n_{PZ}} = 6.8$) blends are reported in Tables 3 and 5. Dash et al. (2012) measured the CO₂ solubility over aqueous solution of 35 mass % AMP and 5 mass % PZ at 30, 40 and 50 °C. The experimental results at 40 °C from this work and from Dash et al. (2012) have been compared and are in good agreement, as shown in Figure S3. Fig. 7a shows the CO₂ solubility experimental data for the three different AMP+PZ blends investigated in this work at 40, 80 and 120 °C. The experimental results show that there is no significant difference in the VLE behavior for a small change in the AMP/PZ molar ratio while the change becomes significant at a higher AMP/PZ ratio. At high CO₂ loading, the sensitivity with the amine concentration becomes less important. This may be due to the small amount of free AMP and PZ at higher CO₂ concentrations. The experimental results suggest that a process model based on a not rigorous thermodynamic model can still effectively predict the CO₂ solubility and the driving force, even when the effect of amine concentration is not accounted for. For example, this approach, as employed by Kvamsdal et al. (2011), is supported by the current experimental findings.

The heat of absorption of CO₂ data for the three different AMP/PZ blends are reported in Table 3. The experimental heat of absorption

data seems to be constant with the temperature within the calculated uncertainty for the whole amine concentration range investigated.

Fig. 7b shows also the comparison of the heat of absorption data at 40 °C. The measured heat of absorption at the CESAR1 concentration and at ($\frac{n_{AMP}}{n_{PZ}} = 1.5$) are very close to each other. This makes sense since the VLE behavior is not significantly different, as shown in the same figure, and neither should the heat of absorption, (Mathias et al., 2012). The heat of absorption for these two solutions is constant to a value of around $-93 \frac{kJ}{mol_{CO_2}}$ up to $0.50 \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP} + mol_{PZ}}$, while it steadily decreases at higher CO₂ loading, as a result of the bicarbonate formation reaction. This behavior is supported by the NMR data collected in this work. The heat of absorption of CO₂ data for the CESAR1 blend measured in this work are higher than the results by Hartono et al. (2021a) in the low-loading region. For the aqueous solution of 35.0 mass % AMP + 5.0 mass % PZ, the heat of absorption steadily decreases with the CO₂ loading, indicating that bicarbonate formation is the main mechanism taking place. This may be due to the high concentration of AMP and low concentration of PZ.

N₂O Solubility data for the CESAR1 blend. The N₂O solubility data for the CESAR1 blend are reported in Table 6 and shown in Fig. 8. The N₂O Henry's constant increases with the temperature and CO₂ load-

Table 5High-pressure CO₂ solubility data for aqueous AMP /PZ solutions, 24.4 mass % AMP and 15.7 mass % PZ [$\frac{mol_{AMP}}{mol_{PZ}} = 1.5$] and 35.0 mass % AMP and 5.0 mass % PZ [$\frac{mol_{AMP}}{mol_{PZ}} = 6.8$].

24.4 mass % AMP + 15.7 mass % PZ																			
373.15 K				393.15 K				403.15 K				413.15 K				423.15 K			
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]
0	0	91.9	-	0	0	182.9	-	0	0	249.6	-	0	0	334.8	-	0	0	444.0	-
0.04	0.00	93.0	1.1	0.04	0.00	185.3	2.4	0.04	0.00	252.3	2.6	0.04	0.00	340.7	5.9	0.05	0.00	457.8	13.8
0.09	0.01	94.2	2.2	0.08	0.01	188.5	5.6	0.08	0.01	258.4	8.7	0.08	0.01	353.6	18.8	0.09	0.01	482.6	38.6
0.13	0.01	95.4	3.4	0.13	0.01	193.9	11.0	0.12	0.01	266.8	17.2	0.12	0.01	371.7	36.9	0.13	0.01	517.4	73.4
0.17	0.01	97.4	5.4	0.17	0.01	200.8	17.9	0.16	0.01	278.4	28.7	0.16	0.01	395.6	60.8	0.17	0.01	564.3	120.3
0.22	0.01	100.1	8.1	0.21	0.01	210.1	27.2	0.20	0.01	294.4	44.8	0.20	0.01	428.3	93.5	0.21	0.01	623.8	179.8
0.26	0.01	103.9	11.9	0.25	0.01	222.9	40.0	0.24	0.01	315.1	65.4	0.24	0.01	467.9	133.1	-	-	-	-
0.30	0.01	109.2	17.2	0.29	0.01	239.6	56.8	0.28	0.01	341.2	91.6	0.28	0.01	518.8	183.9	-	-	-	-
0.35	0.01	116.5	24.5	0.33	0.01	262.8	79.9	-	-	-	-	0.31	0.01	583.2	248.4	-	-	-	-
0.39	0.01	126.0	34.1	0.37	0.01	292.2	109.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.43	0.01	139.5	47.6	0.41	0.01	329.5	146.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.47	0.01	158.0	66.1	0.45	0.01	376.9	194.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.51	0.01	183.7	91.8	0.49	0.01	439.7	256.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.55	0.01	218.8	126.8	0.52	0.01	517.6	334.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.59	0.01	268.2	176.3	0.56	0.01	609.9	427.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.63	0.01	332.1	240.2	0.58	0.01	689.5	506.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35.0 mass % AMP + 5.0 mass % PZ																			
373.15 K				393.15 K				403.15 K				413.15 K				423.15 K			
α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]	α [-]	$u(\alpha)$	P_{tot} [kPa]	P_{CO_2} [kPa]
0	0	94.9	-	0	0	186.2	-	0	0	254.1	-	0	0	340.7	-	0	0	450.0	-
0.07	0.00	100.3	5.4	0.06	0.00	197.1	10.9	0.04	0.00	263.0	9.0	0.05	0.00	362.8	22.1	0.03	0.00	467.8	17.8
0.14	0.01	108.0	13.0	0.12	0.01	223.2	37.0	0.08	0.01	283.6	29.5	0.09	0.01	407.0	66.3	0.06	0.01	504.7	54.8
0.21	0.01	121.6	26.7	0.18	0.01	264.3	78.1	0.12	0.01	314.3	60.3	0.13	0.01	468.9	128.1	0.09	0.01	557.0	107.1
0.27	0.01	143.1	48.2	0.24	0.01	323.0	136.8	0.16	0.01	354.7	100.6	0.17	0.01	546.2	205.4	0.11	0.01	617.5	167.5
0.34	0.01	175.3	80.4	0.30	0.01	402.0	215.8	0.19	0.01	405.4	151.3	0.20	0.01	639.0	298.3	0.13	0.01	655.0	205.0
0.41	0.01	220.4	125.5	0.36	0.01	504.6	318.4	0.23	0.01	465.1	211.1	0.24	0.01	741.4	400.7	0.16	0.01	732.6	282.6
0.47	0.01	282.1	187.2	0.41	0.01	634.8	448.6	0.26	0.01	535.5	281.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.53	0.01	373.6	278.6	-	-	-	-	0.28	0.01	564.9	310.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
II Run								0.29	0.01	599.7	345.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0	0	94.5	-	-	-	-	-	0.3	0.01	623.9	369.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.06	0.00	96.6	2.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.12	0.01	102.3	7.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.18	0.01	112.2	17.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.24	0.01	127.3	32.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.30	0.01	149.0	54.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.36	0.01	179.4	84.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.42	0.01	220.5	126.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.47	0.01	273.0	178.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.49	0.01	299.8	205.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.52	0.01	336.1	241.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.57	0.01	424.3	329.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.61	0.01	522.4	427.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

a) $\alpha = \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP} + mol_{PZ}}$

b) $u(T) = 0.1 K$

c) $u(P_{tot}) = 0.2 kPa$

d) P_{CO_2} was estimated according to: $P_{CO_2} = P_{tot,\alpha} - P_{tot,\alpha=0}$. * P_{CO_2} was not estimated due to high uncertainty.

Table 6
N₂O solubility data for the CESAR1 blend at different temperature and CO₂ loadings.

I Run				II Run			
T [°C]	α [$\frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}+mol_{PZ}}$]	$H_{N_2O}^{app}$ [$\frac{m^3 \cdot kPa}{kmol}$]	$u(H_{N_2O}^{app})$	T [°C]	α [$\frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}+mol_{PZ}}$]	$H_{N_2O}^{app}$ [$\frac{m^3 \cdot kPa}{kmol}$]	$u(H_{N_2O}^{app})$
25.1	0	5876.1	269	25.1	0	5922.8	287
40.1	0	7029.0	347	40.0	0	7008.4	365
59.9	0	8307.0	432	60.0	0	8432.2	469
80.1	0	9425.9	500	80.1	0	9423.7	529
25.3	0.11	6470.3	303	25.1	0.11	6562.6	293
40.0	0.11	7914.2	408	40.0	0.11	8006.4	393
59.8	0.11	9490.2	521	59.8	0.11	9575.9	499
80.0	0.11	10700.5	597	80.1	0.11	10788.2	570
25.9	0.29	7665.5	287	25.1	0.29	7471.8	269
39.9	0.29	9538.5	419	40.0	0.29	9335.6	394
60.1	0.29	11760.4	588	59.9	0.29	11423.6	544
80.0	0.29	13334.9	700	80.0	0.29	13068.6	659
25.2	0.52	8498.7	353	25.3	0.52	8686.0	363
40.0	0.52	10823.7	538	40.0	0.52	11068.0	554
59.8	0.52	13432.8	766	60.0	0.52	13820.0	797
79.7	0.52	15440.3	938	80.0	0.52	15923.5	981

a) $\alpha = \frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}+mol_{PZ}}$
b) $u(T) = 0.1 K$

Fig. 8. Experimental data for N₂O solubility over CO₂ loaded and unloaded CESAR1 blend. (● This work I Run, □ This work II Run), (Green 25 °C, Black 40 °C, Blue 60 °C, Red 80 °C).

ing in the operative range investigated. Therefore, the N₂O solubility decreases as the temperature and CO₂ content in the liquid solution increase. As the CO₂ content increases, the ionic strength in the solution increases, promoting the salting-out effect. This behavior is in line with other amine systems (Hartono et al., 2014). The experimental data show a good repeatability, the deviation between the two runs is explained by the calculated uncertainty. The measured data can be used to estimate the Henry's Constant of CO₂ via the N₂O analogy. These data are of crucial importance in the thermodynamic and kinetic modelling of CO₂ capture system (Monteiro et al., 2015) and fill a gap in the open literature.

pH data for aqueous AMP/PZ blend. The measured pH data are presented in Table 7 and the results show that the pH decreases by increasing of the CO₂ concentration as expected since the solution becomes more acidic. Furthermore, the results show that the pH for un-

Table 7
pH data for aqueous AMP/PZ solution at 50 °C and atmospheric pressure.

AMP [$\frac{m_{AMP}}{m_{tot}}$]	PZ [$\frac{m_{PZ}}{m_{tot}}$]	[AMP]/[PZ] [$\frac{mol}{mol}$]	α [$\frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}+mol_{PZ}}$]	pH
26.8	12.8	2	0.00	12.14
25.8	12.3		0.20	9.96
25.3	12.1		0.30	9.81
24.8	11.8		0.40	9.46
23.9	11.4		0.60	8.76
51.2	8.5	6	0.00	12.36
50.2	8.3		0.09	10.30
50.3	8.0		0.13	10.09
50.0	7.9		0.17	10.01
48.9	7.7		0.25	9.85
17.9	41.8	0.4	0.00	13.21
17.2	41.4		0.09	10.82
16.9	41.1		0.13	10.62
16.6	41.0		0.17	10.57
16.0	40.9		0.25	10.42

a) $u(T) = 0.2 K$ b) $u(P) = 0.2 kPa$ c) $u(pH) = 0.02$

loaded solutions increases as a function of the alkaline concentration. The pH of the CESAR1 solvent with loadings from 0 to 0.60 $\frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP}+mol_{PZ}}$ was measured without any precipitation issues, however, for the higher total concentrations of amine (up to 60.0 mass %), higher loadings were not possible due to precipitation issues.

NMR-data for aqueous AMP/PZ blend. The experimental NMR data collected in this work are reported in Table 8. The reactions describing the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ are reported in Morlando et al. (2024a) and involves 15 different species: AMP, protonated AMP (AMPH⁺), AMP carbamate (AMP₂COO⁻), PZ, protonated piperazine (PZH⁺), PZ deprotonated piperazine (PZH₂²⁺), piperazine carbamate (PZCOO⁻), piperazine dicarbamate (PZ(COO⁻)₂), protonated piperazine carbamate (HPZCOO), bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) and carbonate (CO₃²⁻) and H⁺ and OH⁻ ions. Due to the fast rate of the protonation reactions, it is not possible to distinguish a molecule and its protonated product (Ciftja et al., 2013), therefore, the results are reported in terms of

Table 8Speciation data for CO₂ loaded CESAR1 (3.0 M AMP + 1.5 M PZ) solvent and the aqueous 1.5 M AMP + 0.75 M PZ solvent at 25 °C and atmospheric pressure.

3 M AMP + 1.5 M PZ (26.6 mass % AMP + 12.8 mass % PZ)									
CO ₂ Loading $\left[\frac{\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{mol}_{\text{AMP}}+\text{mol}_{\text{PZ}}}\right]$		Mole Fraction							
α NMR	α IC	AMP/AMPH ⁺	AMP ₂ COO ⁻	PZ/PZH ⁺ /PZH ₂ ²⁺	PZCOO ⁻ /HPZCOO	PZ(COO ⁻) ₂	HCO ₃ ⁻ /CO ₃ ²⁻		
0.00	0.00	0.0835	0.0000	0.0413	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000		
0.04	0.04	0.0857	0.0000	0.0383	0.0048	0.0002	0.0003		
0.09	0.10	0.0818	0.0003	0.0289	0.0091	0.0006	0.0007		
0.19	0.20	0.0920	0.0003	0.0236	0.0176	0.0031	0.0021		
0.28	0.29	0.0830	0.0004	0.0165	0.0200	0.0059	0.0034		
0.38	0.39	0.0854	0.0007	0.0100	0.0217	0.0104	0.0056		
0.49	0.50	0.0691	0.0010	0.0067	0.0187	0.0123	0.0080		
0.57	0.57	0.0872	0.0013	0.0056	0.0194	0.0194	0.0161		
1.5 M AMP + 0.75 M PZ (13.5 mass % AMP + 6.5 mass % PZ)									
CO ₂ Loading $\left[\frac{\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{mol}_{\text{AMP}}+\text{mol}_{\text{PZ}}}\right]$		Mole Fraction							
α NMR	α IC	AMP/AMPH ⁺	AMP ₂ COO ⁻	PZ/PZH ⁺ /PZH ₂ ²⁺	PZCOO ⁻ /HPZCOO	PZ(COO ⁻) ₂	HCO ₃ ⁻ /CO ₃ ²⁻		
0.00	0.00	0.0332	0.0000	0.0168	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000		
0.09	0.10	0.0322	0.0001	0.0134	0.0032	0.0002	0.0010		
0.19	0.20	0.0334	0.0001	0.0099	0.0056	0.0007	0.0022		
0.39	0.40	0.0312	0.0003	0.0056	0.0078	0.0029	0.0047		
0.59	0.60	0.0352	0.0003	0.0032	0.0087	0.0061	0.0102		
0.70	0.72	0.0361	0.0003	0.0025	0.0089	0.0067	0.0155		
0.78	0.81	0.0322	0.0002	0.0020	0.0096	0.0054	0.0179		

Fig. 9. Experimental speciation data for aqueous 3.0 M AMP + 1.5 M PZ (CESAR1) and aqueous 1.5 M AMP + 0.75 M PZ solution as a function of the CO₂ loading.

6 lumped groups: AMP/AMPH⁺, AMP₂COO⁻, PZ/PZH⁺/PZH₂²⁺, PZCOO⁻/HPZCOO, PZ(COO⁻)₂ and HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻.

The experimental NMR data are shown in Fig. 9. The experimental data shows that at low CO₂ loading, up to 0.40 $\frac{\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{mol}_{\text{AMP}}+\text{mol}_{\text{PZ}}}$, the dissolved CO₂ is prevalently bound as PZCOO⁻/HPZCOO, the PZ(COO⁻)₂ gets to be a major product from 0.20 $\frac{\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{mol}_{\text{AMP}}+\text{mol}_{\text{PZ}}}$ and steadily increases as a result of the carbamation of PZCOO⁻ up to 0.70 $\frac{\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{mol}_{\text{AMP}}+\text{mol}_{\text{PZ}}}$, at higher loading the reaction is reversed and the PZ(COO⁻)₂ concentration decreases. PZ/PZH⁺/PZH₂²⁺ decreases steadily along the overall range of CO₂ concentration as results of the reactions forming PZ carbamate species. The AMP₂COO⁻ is a minor product over the whole range of CO₂ loading investigated. Consequently, the AMP/AMPH⁺ is rather constant indicating that the protonation of the AMP and reaction forming HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻ are the major mechanism of CO₂ capture for the AMP solvent. The concentration of HCO₃⁻/CO₃²⁻ steadily increases as a function of CO₂ loading.

The NMR experimental data collected in this work can be used in the fitting of a rigorous thermodynamic framework and fill an experimental gap in the open literature.

Conclusion

This work provides experimental thermodynamic data for CO₂ absorption using aqueous AMP/PZ solutions. CO₂ solubility over aqueous AMP/PZ solutions, including the CESAR1 blend, were measured up to 150 °C, broadening the temperature and CO₂ loading range previously available in the literature. The experimental results show that a slight variation in the AMP/PZ concentration ratio has minimal impact on CO₂ solubility and heat of absorption. However, increasing the AMP/PZ ratio from 2 (the CESAR1 blend) to 6.8 leads to observable changes in both properties, with trends increasingly resembling those of an aqueous AMP solution.

The heat of absorption of CO₂ was measured as a function of temperature (from 40 °C to 80 °C), CO₂ loading and AMP/PZ molar ratio. The

results indicate that the heat of absorption is constant with the temperature and that the heat of absorption behavior is a function of the CO₂ loading and the amount of sterically primary amine (AMP) and diamine (PZ) in the liquid solvent. The N₂O solubility was measured for the CESAR1 blend from 25 °C to 80 °C and 0 to 0.52 $\frac{mol_{CO_2}}{mol_{AMP} + mol_{PZ}}$. The results indicate that the N₂O solubility decreases as a function of temperature and CO₂ loading over the whole range of operative conditions investigated. Speciation data for the CESAR1 blend and a blend 1.5 M AMP + 0.75 M PZ were obtained by NMR spectroscopy. The results indicate that, at low CO₂ loading, the CO₂ is bound as *PZCOO*⁻/*HPZCOO* and at higher CO₂ loading *PZ(COO*⁻)₂ and *HCO*₃⁻/*CO*₃²⁻ are the most abundant products. These data provide a broader understanding of the chemical mechanism taking place when CO₂ chemical reacts with the CESAR1 blend.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Diego Morlando: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ardi Hartono:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hanna K. Knuutila:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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